

Penalty at Islamic Financial Institutions: Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding Penalty in Islamic Financial Institutions with a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Penalty on Islamic Financial Institutions " within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Penalty in Islamic Financial Institutions based on journals that have been collected. The research results show that There are 9 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding Penalty at Islamic Financial Institutions. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Penalty in Islamic Financial Institutions, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Penalty; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic Financial Institutions

Introduction

Banking has a very important position in a country's economy. The growth of sharia banking in Indonesia continues to increase every year and is spread throughout Indonesia. This is the basic function of Islamic Financial Institutions to collect excess public capital and distribute it to those in need by selling products and carrying out transactions according to the direction of the Sharia Supervisory Board. Responsible for supervising the operational activities of Islamic Financial Institutions in accordance with sharia provisions or banks which are called financial intermediaries, namely intermediaries between savers and investors, and banks are development facilitators (development of banking function performance related to objectives and equity).

The performance of Islamic banks is a key parameter that determines the position of Islamic banks in the banking industry. In Indonesia, sharia banking performance measures are reported by Bank Indonesia (BI) using financial information. Sharia banking is part of Islamic values that manage the economic sector of society and is an application of the sharia economic system that is not separated from other aspects of comprehensive and global Islamic law. In this case, Islamic banks act as financial intermediaries and have requirements that must be met by their customers (debtors) in order to be able to lend funds for equity and development to those in need.

Each Islamic bank makes differences in formulating fine fees on financing depending on the vulnerability or duration of the financing amount which is determined based on the level of financing required by the customer. The more Murabahah loan funds the client requests, the higher the fine the client receives. When signing the contract and Ijab Qabul, the client is informed about the Murabahah loan rates. If the fine fee is not included in the bank margin, but the fee is directed to Baitulmaal Muamalat, which is used as a charity fund for community activities.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding Penalty in Islamic financial institutions using library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics regarding Penalty in Islamic Financial Institutions, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Penalty in Islamic Financial Institutions, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

Penalty are a type of punishment that involves paying a certain amount of money. Sharia Bank is a financial institution that carries out business activities based on sharia principles in its operations and serves payments or public financing. Conventional banks are business entities that collect money from the public and channel it back to the community in the form of credit or other loans aimed at improving the standard of living of the general public. However, conventional banks are different from Islamic banks because they charge interest on all types of credit or loans.

Islamic Financial inclusion refers to efforts to ensure that all individuals and economic entities, regardless of their economic, social, or geographic background, have fair and appropriate access to financial products and services that comply with sharia principles. Sharia principles are Islamic economic rules and guidelines that prohibit riba (interest), excessive speculation, and investment in businesses that are forbidden under Islamic law. Islamic Financial inclusion includes a variety of financial products and services, such as savings, microfinance, insurance, investment and other financial instruments, that comply with sharia principles. The aim of Islamic Financial inclusion is to increase public access to financial services that are in accordance with the values and principles of the Islamic religion. Islamic Financial inclusion has a positive impact on the economy, including reducing poverty, improving community welfare, and strengthening financial system stability. Apart from that, Islamic Financial inclusion also supports the development of the Islamic Financial sector as a whole, which involves financial institutions such as sharia banks, sharia insurance companies and sharia capital markets.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of literature study research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, literature study research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and

organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Bibliometric studies are a research method used to analyze and measure scientific publications in a particular field, using quantitative data. In bibliometric studies, the data analyzed includes information about the number of publications, authors, subjects, publication sources, citations, and impact factor. The goal of bibliometric studies is to provide an overview of trends and patterns in scientific publications, as well as measure the impact of these publications on the academic community and industry. Bibliometric studies can be used to identify emerging research areas, measure research performance, and compare performance between researchers, institutions, or countries. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out using bibliometric software, such as Web of Science, Scopus, or Google Scholar. Bibliometric methods can also be used to conduct qualitative analysis, such as content analysis or other qualitative analysis, to understand the issues expressed in certain scientific publications.

VOSviewer is open source software used in bibliometric studies to visualize and analyze the network of links between documents or scientific publications. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data collected from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. VOSviewer can be used to perform quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as cluster identification, citation analysis, and topic mapping. In cluster analysis, VOSviewer can group scientific publications into similar groups based on their association with a particular topic. Citation analysis can be used to identify the most cited scientific publications in a research field. Topic mapping can be used to identify the most widely discussed research topics in a field. One of the advantages of VOSviewer is its ability to produce attractive and easy-to-understand visualizations, such as heatmaps, network graphs and topic trees. This visualization can help researchers understand patterns and trends in bibliometric data more easily and quickly. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, academics, and practitioners in various research fields, including social science, information science, health, and information technology.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in library research. The object of the research is Penalty at Islamic Financial Institutions. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about Penalty originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keywords " Sharia Bank Penalty " and "Sharia Bank Collateral" for the entire year period (2013 -2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of

bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) map topics, methods, research findings, and research gaps based on Library Research studies.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Sharia Bank Penalty on Islamic Financial Institutions

The results of a search for scientific journals on Sharia Bank Penalty in Islamic Financial Institutions from 2013 to 2022 show the development of journal publications every year, especially in the last 5 years. From the search results, 40 article titles were obtained from accredited national and international journals.

Table 1: Scientific publication data regarding Bank Penalty regarding Bank Penalty at Islamic Financial Institutions by year period

Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles
2013	1	2017	3	2020	7
2015	2	2018	9	2021	8
2016	1	2019	6	2022	3

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In table 2, there are 39 affiliates/institutions publishing research articles regarding Sharia Bank Penalty in Islamic Financial Institutions.

Table 2. Data from journal publishing institutions regarding Bank Penalty on Islamic Financial Institutions

Name of Institution/Affiliation	Number of Publications
Eksisbank, Research Journal, Maliyah	2
Al-Muamalat, Al-Amwal, Al-Huquq, Al-Ihda', Al-Intaj, Al-Iqtishadiyah, Al-Manahij, Al-Muamalat, Amwaluna, At-Tijarah, Az-Zarqa', Cakrawala, Diponegoro, Eksyar, El-Faqih, Global Review of Islamic Economics and Business, INDONESIAN JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING AND GOVERNANCE, Inovbiz, Journal of Enterprise and Development (JED), Journal of Islamic Law Studies, Sharia Journal, JURIS, AKUNESA Accounting Journal, Sharia Economic Journal, Accounting and Banking (JESKaPe), Iqtisaduna Journal, ISLAMIKA JOURNAL, Manage Journal: Social Sciences Journal, Repertorium Journal, MUAMALATUN, Qawanin, SEISENSE, Share, Shirkah, TSAQFAH	1

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Table 3 shows that all researchers have only published an article once.

Table 3. Researcher regarding Bank Penalty on Islamic Financial Institutions

Researcher	Institution
Pedagogita Rakhmah, Suad Qurrotul Aini	UIN Sunan Ampel Surabaya
Bai Sutihat; Ade Mulyana	UIN Sultan Maulana Hasanuddin Banten
Asep Arifin; Meti Hasanah	UIN Sunan Gunung Djati Bandung
Muchlish Khomayny, Muhammad Wahyuddin Badullah	UIN Alauddin Makassar
Ika Meliyana Wahyuni; Muhammad Iqbal Fasa; Suharto, Dini Maulana Lestari; Abdul Qoyum	UIN Sunan Kalijaga Yogyakarta
Eco Bahtiar	UIN Mataram
Riansyah Rainal Purnama; Siti Jahroh; Moch. Hadi Santoso; Ahmad Rifai	UIN Ar-Raniry
Irfan Harmoko	IAIN Kediri
Idris Yahaya Adamu, Aqeel Akhtar; Fahad Ahmed Qureshi; Mubeen Butt	IAIN Surakarta
Yoesrizal M. Yoesoef; Nisak Khalista	IAIN Langsa
Moch. Endang Djunaedi; Muhammad Maulana Yusuf	IAIN Sheikh Nurjati Cirebon
Fadli	IAIN Batusangkar
Nonie Afrianty	IAIN Bengkulu
Fathul Aminudin Aziz	IAIN Purwokerto
Ahmad Maulidizen	IAIN Kudus
Aulil Amri, Muhammad Al-Mustafa	IAIN Lhokseumawe
Wasilul Chair; Kudrat Abdillah	IAIN Madura
Maman Surahman; Nurrohman	Bandung Islamic University
Elfadhli; Frel M. Rizqi; Iqbal Sulaiman; Fatimah Setia Wardhani	Muhammadiyah University of Riau
Riduwan; Dwi Santosa Pambudi; Muhammad Alfian Lukluk Firdausi; Nurul Huda	Muhammadiyah University of Magelang
Faith Setya Budi	Muhammad Arsyad Al Banjary Islamic University of Kalimantan
Mhd. Yes, Harapan	University of Indonesia
Rabita Asri Jayendati; Erman Denny Arfianto	Diponegoro University
Burhanuddin Harapan; Teuku Arie Azhari	Sebelas Maret University, Surakarta
Dedy Rachmat	Bengkalis State Polytechnic
Mr Nurhadi	LIPI
Muhammad Sultan Aziz	IAI Faqih Asy'ari Kediri
Laode Arahman Nasir; Beware	Agung Podomoro University
Yulia Febriyati	STAI Nurul Falah Airmolek
Moch. Cahyo Sucipto; Rina Nurhayati; Ida Rosdiana, Putranto Sigit; Ahmad Saepudin; Saeful Bahri; Yulia Purnama	STIES Indonesia Purwakarta
Alimin; Rizal Fahlefi	Darussalam Gontor University

internal, debt installment, delay, economic activity, event, existence, fee, financing al murabaha good faith, research results show, research results show, imposition, interview, Islamic banking Islamic law, guarantee, keywords, late payment, mui law, non-performing financing, party, penalty, application of Penalty, policy, presence, problematic financing, PT Bank BNI Syariah, Sharia reasoning deduction, Tawidh, the aim and research is, will.

- Cluster 3. The blue color consists of 31, namely: author, sharia bank, collateral appraiser, collateral implementation, company, competence, sharia credit card, etc., effect, factor, fatwa no impact, Indonesia, Islamic credit card, Islamic economic system, masalah, motivation, mudaraba financing contract, mui ix, murabahah, order, performance, quantitative approach, questionnaire, account of, research, respondent, satisfaction, sharia banking, sharia banking practice, Source, variable.
- Cluster 4. The yellow color consists of 29 topics, namely: able customer, amount, bmt, compensation contract agreement, conventional financial institution, Penalty, den muina, fatwa, fatwa etc. mut no, fund, Islamic law, ifi, implementation, Income, sharia credit, late charge, late payment, Islamic Financial institutions, Iks, capable customers, practice, question, requirement, rule, sharia pawnshop, sharia pawnshops, social, function, tawid.
- Cluster 5. The color purple consists of 28 topics, namely: auction process, auction result, auction service office bank, bank BNI Syarah Pontianak branch, BNI, BNI Syariah, BNI Syariah Bank, collateral auction, comparison, data, debt, debt, document, implementation process, kpknl, mechanism, pontianak, pontianak state wealth, price, proceed, process, pt bni tbk pontianak branch, qualitative research, researcher, sale, time, total debt.
- Cluster 6. The light blue color consists of 21 topics, namely: bri syariah kep kopo, capable customer, capacity, customer, date, etc. mui ix, end, form, money, obligation, payment, micro product financing, point, provision, punishment, sanction, social fund, status, sum, tazit fine, tazir principle.
- Cluster 7. The orange color consists of 18 topics, namely: account, account officer, analysis, character, collateral value, credit, influence, interest preference Islamic bank, leverage, net working capital, non-Muslim, npf, person, profitability, sharia commercial bank, study, value.
- Cluster 8. The brown color consists of 17 topics, namely: regulations, bmt pas, fact, field, field research, fource majeure general knowledge, installment, member, need, penalty system, bank sharia, sharia economic perspective, Islamic Financial institution, sharia financing product, solution, type.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Application of Penalty in Islamic Financial Institutions

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 9 topics related to the application of Penalty to Islamic Financial Institutions, namely:

First, the accounting treatment of Penalty. The accounting treatment of Penalty at Islamic banks can vary depending on the type of transaction and products provided by the bank. However, some information that can be taken from the search results is as follows: In the application of accounting for Penalty on sharia credit cards, there are no regulations or PSAK that apply in Indonesia. The concept of fine treatment in murabahah financing transactions is explained

in the Statement of Financial Accounting Standards (PSAK 102) concerning Murabahah Accounting and DSNMUI Fatwa No. 17/DSN-MUI/IX/2000. In Islamic banks, Penalty are based on the principle of ta'zir, namely to provide punishment so that customers are more disciplined in carrying out their obligations. Penalty do not include usury because usury is an illegal increase in income (batil). Penalty must be included in social funds which are usually intended for the poor and needy.

Second, the application of Penalty on credit cards, rental contracts, iB Hasanah Card, hajj arrum financing, Murabahah financing, bai' bitsaman ajil, and late payments of Education Development Contributions/SPP.

Third, the application of Penalty according to the DSN-MUI fatwa (No. 17 of 2000), Islamic law, Islamic public finance, fiqh, sharia economics, and Law no. 21 of 2008.

Fourth, the application of Penalty in sharia banking, Baitul Mal wat Tamwil/BMT, universities, sharia leasing, Federal International Finance /FIF, and sharia pawnshops.

Fifth, the position of collateral and Penalty. Guarantees in Islamic banks are an application of the principle of banking prudence or prudential banking and are based on sharia principles to reduce risks in financing. Imposition of guarantees on Islamic banks must pay attention to sharia principles and must not give the impression of mixing the rules and principles of Islamic banks with conventional banks. Meanwhile, the position of Penalty at sharia banks is based on the principle of justice and must be included in social funds intended for the poor and needy. Penalty on sharia banks must pay attention to sharia principles and must not be used as income or provide profits to sharia banks.

Sixth, eliminating the policy of late Penalty for non-performing financing (NPF). Eliminating the policy of late Penalty for non-performing financing (NPF) in sharia banks can have both positive and negative impacts. The following is some information that can be taken from the search results: Positive: Eliminating the policy of late Penalty on problematic financing can have a positive effect on customers, thereby encouraging customers to be more disciplined in fulfilling their obligations. Eliminating the policy of late Penalty for problematic financing can have a positive impact on marketing. Negative: Eliminating the policy of late Penalty on problematic financing can increase the level of Non-Performing Financing (NPF). Problematic financing or NPF is a phenomenon that occurs in the sharia banking industry because one of the main activities of sharia banks is the distribution of financing. In recent developments, problematic financing or NPF of Islamic banks has turned out to be relatively high. In fact, according to 2015 data, problematic financing of Islamic banks is higher than conventional banks. Therefore, eliminating the policy of late Penalty on problematic financing must be considered carefully so as not to increase the NPF level. From the information above, it can be concluded that eliminating the policy of late Penalty for problematic financing in Islamic banks can have both positive and negative impacts. Eliminating the fine policy can have a positive effect on customers and marketing, but can increase the NPF level. Therefore, eliminating the fine policy must be considered carefully so as not to increase the NPF level.

Seventh, the treatment of Penalty is based on the al-'adl concept. In Islamic banks, Penalty must be given based on the concept of al-'adl or justice. Penalty may only be given to customers who can afford it but delay payment. In distribution, the fine must be used as social funds and not used as income or providing profits to sharia banks. The imposition of Penalty aims to make

customers/consumers more disciplined in carrying out their obligations and to achieve justice as one of the principles of implementing sharia banking between capital providers and capital users. Penalty can also be used to deal with problematic financing, which can have a negative impact on the bank, such as non-payment of partial or full financing, which can have an impact on the health level of bank liquidity and reduce the level of depositor confidence. Funds derived from Penalty must be put into social funds intended for the poor and needy. These funds can be used for various activities, such as providing social assistance, infrastructure development, and community economic development. Apart from that, Islamic banks can use funds from Penalty to improve the quality of services and infrastructure, so as to increase customer and public confidence in the bank.

Eighth, utilization of funds resulting from Penalty. Funds resulting from Penalty at Islamic banks must be used appropriately so that they can provide benefits to society. The following is some information that can be taken from the search results: Penalty on Islamic banks must be included in social funds intended for the poor and needy. Social funds intended for the poor and needy can be used for various activities, such as providing social assistance, infrastructure development and community economic development. Sharia banks can use funds from Penalty to improve the quality of services and infrastructure, so as to increase customer and public confidence in the bank. Funds from Penalty can also be used to deal with problematic financing, which can have a negative impact on the bank, such as non-payment of partial or full financing, which can impact the health of the bank's liquidity and reduce the level of depositors' confidence. From the information above, it can be concluded that funds resulting from Penalty at Islamic banks must be used appropriately so that they can provide benefits to society. These funds must be included in social funds intended for the poor and needy, which can be used for various activities. In addition, Islamic banks can use funds from Penalty to improve the quality of services and infrastructure, as well as handle problematic financing. This can increase customer and public confidence in the bank.

Ninth, the effect of Penalty on efforts to prevent problematic financing. Penalty for problematic financing can have an impact on efforts to prevent problematic financing in Islamic banks. The following is some information that can be taken from the research results: Penalty can have a deterrent effect on problem financing customers so that they can encourage customers to be more disciplined in fulfilling their obligations. In applying Penalty to problematic financing, Islamic banks must pay attention to the principles of justice and expediency. Problematic financing can have a negative impact on banks, such as non-payment of partial or full financing, which can impact the health level of bank liquidity and reduce the level of depositors' confidence. Sharia banks must develop the appropriate steps needed to handle problematic financing as a step to revitalize and improve the health of the bank. The application of Penalty to Islamic banks must pay attention to sharia principles and must not be included in the bank's income. Penalty must be included in social funds intended for the poor and needy. From the information above, it can be concluded that Penalty for problematic financing can have a deterrent effect on customers and encourage customers to be more disciplined in fulfilling their obligations. However, Islamic banks must pay attention to the principles of justice and expediency in implementing Penalty. Apart from that, Islamic banks must develop appropriate steps to handle problematic financing as a step to restore

and improve the health of the bank. Finally, Penalty must be included in social funds intended for the poor and needy.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 9 research topic mappings using literature studies regarding Penalty at Islamic Financial Institutions.

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